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4. The success and failure of promotion schemes will eventually be judged by the increase in footfall with comparison to increase in sales. An increase in footfall without a corresponding increase in the sale would imply that the promotional schemes were not able to attract the customer and hence, the retailer has failed upon converting footfalls into sales. Similarly, if an increase in footfall is not observed, it would imply that the promotional scheme has failed altogether as it was not even sufficient to pull the customer to the store.

5. Customer, specifically the value customer does not consider the party which is offering the discount. For the customer, it is eventually the price he pays from his pocket.

6. Sales promotion can be a vital tool in increasing the competitiveness of organized retail against unorganized retail.

Thus it can be concluded that the elasticity of demand must be considered at the time of offering discount. Also the buying behaviors need not be directly related to income groups. A customer whose rising income has transcended him to high income bracket may retain its old buying habit. Lastly, despite of consolidation and high quality at offer, organized retail still has to compete against unorganized retail considering its stone throw away location advantage.

Finally, it can be recommended that retailers should not broadly divide their customers on the basis of their income groups when giving discounts and the nature and perish ability of a product at the customer premises should be considered during the offering of discount.

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AN ANALYSIS OF RETAIL PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR TO DEVELOP RETAIL STRATEGY FOR GLOBAL RETAILERS

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ABSTRACT

The retail sector is one of the fastest emerging sectors in India. Western pattern of retail formats in India do not suit people and culture. The researcher has endeavoured to judge the differences in retail purchase factors across customers of different locational points and suggest appropriate measures for developing effective global market strategies with local orientation. The outcome of the study undertaken in Pune (Maharashtra) reveals that there is no significant difference in overall retail expectation in three urban and suburban areas in case of grocery and food purchases. A significant difference has been observed in the apparel sector. In the case of apparel proximity, there is no importance attached to the three different locational points. For grocery and food the respondents have given weightage to nearby stores whereas for apparel they prefer to travel some distance. Regarding communication, the opinions expressed were found alike for grocery and food but different for apparels. Price has been found alike for grocery and food while difference has been notable in the apparel sector area - wise. Service is also one of the important areas.

Retail format has to be Indianized in terms of communication, assortment, ambience and service. People are still price sensitive. Regarding ambience of the store, people prefer western format. The global retailers have to redesign the retail format strategies on the basis of customized regional approach. The analytical corpus of the research makes it amply evident that exclusive showrooms of branded companies and goods (viz.

Wal Mart) are not feasible in the Indian scenario and they have to reframe their strategies.

Key Words: Retail Management, Purchase Behaviour, Retail Strategy, Global retailing.

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INTRODUCTION

The retail sector is one of the fastest emerging sectors in India. According to Mc Kinsey Report 2007, India is the second largest market in the world. The worth of transition is Rs. 17 trillions at present and it is expected to cross Rs. 70 trillion by 2025 AD. Food and Grocery is the second largest segment of the retail market. As per KSA Techno Pak Report (2007), these constitute 70% of the total retail sales. In India, food and grocery retail business has been estimated to be worth Rs. 7,43,900 crore out of Rs. 12,00,000 crore retail market and it is also noticeable that grocery stores dominate the retail market. Around 99 percent market is well dominated by neighborhood grocery stores.

No doubt, retail industry is one of the largest industries in India, but it is highly fragmented

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IJMC has three editors and an associate editor. The editors have geographic responsibilities so that articles and cases can be accepted from the international domain. Covering Eastern Europe, Western and Central Europe and the rest of The World. The IJMC has published papers from academics in the USA, Australia, Europe, The Asian subcontinent and South America. It is truly an international peer assessed source of output.

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